

Comparison of Nursing Care Satisfaction Among Orthopaedic Patients in Two Selected Teaching Hospitals in Osun State

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Abstract

The provision of quality health services is a crucial competitive advantage of health service providers. Nursing care plays a major role in the health care services. Orthopaedic patients require a greater level of care as a result of several possible complications, increased vulnerability, potential cardio-pulmonary compromise and requirement of general concerns. The study therefore compared nursing care satisfaction among orthopaedic patients in two selected teaching hospitals in Osun State. The study adopted the descriptive research design of the survey type. The population study comprised all patients scheduled for elective and emergency, Orthopaedics surgeries in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo during the study period. All the available patients were recruited within two months of data collection. A standardized tool of the Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality Questionnaire (PSNCQQ) was adapted for data collection. The instrument was validated by subjecting it to be reviewed by experts of nursing education and Tests & Measurement. The findings of the study revealed that 66.0% of the patients in OAUTHC had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing while 62.5% of the patients in LAUTECH also had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing. It was also revealed that there was no difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in OAUTHC and LAUTECH. It was recommended among others that

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nursing care in the two hospitals (OAUTHC and LAUTECH) in Osun State should be adequately improved so as to achieve high level of the patient's satisfaction with nursing care.

Keywords: Comparison, patient satisfaction, nursing care, orthopaedic patients,

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Introduction

Nursing care plays a major role in the health care services. Orthopaedic patients require a greater level of care as a result of several possible complications, increased vulnerability, potential cardio-pulmonary compromise and requirement of general concerns. Management of these complications requires understanding of preoperative conditions, intra-operative management and early recognition of any signs and treatment of postoperative complications. Delayed and inappropriate care can lead to poor outcomes and avoidable deaths. Adeyemo, Michael, Okunlade and Okpala (2016) reported that majority of accident victims that come into the hospital end up in Orthopaedic wards. This fact signifies the need for improved health care for patients in the orthopaedic wards.

The achievement of outstanding patient satisfaction and building a culture of client service distinction in hospitals is dependent on finding the intangible aspects of expectation that contribute to patient satisfaction (Riley, Gordan, Hudak & Rindal, 2014). Assessing patients on what they think about the care and treatment they are receiving is an important process towards improvement of the quality of care which helps to ensure that the health services are meeting patients' needs.

Patient satisfaction is the most important indicator of high-quality health care and is used for the assessment and planning of health care (Lyngkhai & Brindha, 2015; Joshi, Purani & Kartha, 2013). There is a positive correlation between patient satisfaction and nursing care. Patient satisfaction increases in an organization where more personalized nursing care is given (Pitkaaho, Partanen, Miettinen & Vehvilanen-Julkunen, 2015). Thomas, Newcomb and Fusco (2018) described how to increase patient satisfaction with multidimensional nursing approaches. They gathered data by employing two scales consisting of patient satisfaction and nursing approaches. The findings of the study showed that multifaceted staff interventions improved patients' satisfaction with nursing care.

The experience of the researcher in the last 29 years at the clinical setting was the way Orthopaedic wards are always having barely vacant beds. Orthopaedic patients do not want to stay long in the hospital environment. The Elderly ones may have the opinion that the Orthopaedic illness may end their lives, they will prefer to die at home instead of the hospital. Nursing care for hospitalized adults entails primarily curative and restorative health and it is expected that approaches to the delivery of care including attitude of nurses have changed positively over the years towards effective nursing care. Alsaqri (2016) opined that when the patients have many options, future return to the same healthcare provider will depend on how satisfied they are with the health care settings.

Based on the foregoing, the study compared nursing care satisfaction among orthopaedic patients in two selected teaching hospitals in Osun State. The study specifically examined:

- i. the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife;
- ii. the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo; and
- iii. the difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo

Research Questions

The study has the following research questions:

1. What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife
2. What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo

Research Hypothesis

This hypothesis was generated for this study:

1. There is no significant difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo

Research Setting

Osun state is a Southwestern inland state of Nigeria. Osun State was created on August on 27th 1991. It is located on latitude 7° 30'N and longitude 4°30'E. It covers total land mass of about 12,820 square kilometres. The major ethnic-groups in Osun state are Yoruba people, although there are other ethnic groups from other parts of Nigeria. Yoruba and English are the official languages of the dwellers of the state. According to the 2006 National Population Census, Osun States has a population of 3,423,535 inhabitants, made up of 1,740,619 males and 1,682,916 females (National Population Commission, 2006). There are four teaching hospitals in Osun state namely; Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals complex, Ile-Ife and Ilesha, Osun State University Teaching Hospital, Asubiaro, Osogbo and Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo.

Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals complex, Ile-Ife (OAUTHC) is one of the Federal Tertiary health institutions in Nigeria. It serves as a referral center for other hospitals in the neighbouring states in the Southwestern, Nigeria. The institution is well equipped with new technological structures and highly experienced man-power including specialized nurses in different fields of care, medical doctors as physician and surgeons, laboratory scientists, pharmacists and other paramedical workers. The services offered in the hospital include but not limited to renal replacement therapy, accident and emergency care, conventional and laparoscopic surgical services. The patients' admission and treatment outcomes have been very encouraging.

Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osogbo (LAUTECH) was established in the year 2000 by Oyo and Osun state governments. It is a 350 bedded hospital situated at Idi-Seke area of station road, Osogbo. The facility has 2,017 staff, comprising of core professionals and other supporting professionals. It is a specialist hospital which covers surgical and medical specialties. It also offers services on radiological diagnosis, endoscope, pediatriatric, dialysis, ophthalmology, physiotherapy, cardiology and laboratory services. This informs the choice of these hospitals as the research settings.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive research design of the survey type. It seeks information about the outcome of clinical care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex, Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola Teaching Hospital, Osogbo towards Orthopaedic patient's satisfaction with nursing care. The population study comprised all patients scheduled for elective and emergency, Orthopaedics surgeries in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo during the study period. All the available patients

were recruited within two months of data collection. The exclusion criteria include comorbidity in the orthopaedic patients, patients older than 60 years and cases involving amputations.

As this study seeks to compare satisfaction with nursing care among orthopaedic patients in two selected hospitals (OAUTHC and LAUTECH) in Osun State, Nigeria, a standardized tool of the Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality Questionnaire (PSNCQQ) was adapted. The responses of the patients are taken using a 5-point Likert-type scale. The scoring of the scale was 5 = excellent, 4 = very good, 3 = good, 2 = fair, 1 = poor.

The instrument was validated by subjecting it to be reviewed by experts of nursing education and Tests & Measurement. They appraised the items on the basis of ambiguity, relevance and sentence structure. The reliability coefficient was estimated using the Cronbach's Alpha formula. The obtained Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was 0.94 which is considered reliable for the purpose of this study. A representative sample of 80 which is crucial for the quality of the results was selected, administered and collected. A total of 58 patients who adequately completed the instruments were selected and used for the study.

Data collected were analysed with the aid of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The research questions were subjected to descriptive statistics while the hypothesis was tested using inferential statistics of t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Socio-demographic data of Respondents

The socio-demographic data computed below include age, gender, language, marital status, employment status, and educational background of the respondents. The information is important for the interpretation of the findings presented later in this study and it shows the representativeness of the study.

Table 1: Demographic data

Demographic	N (%)
Age (Years)	
< 20	3 (5.2)
20-29	15 (25.9)
30-39	23 (39.7)
40-49	8 (13.6)
50-59	4 (6.8)
60-69	2 (3.4)
70 And Above	3 (5.2)
Total	58 (100)
Gender	
Male	35 (60.3)
Female	23 (39.7)
Total	58 (100)
Language	
Yoruba	45 (77.6)
Hausa	4 (6.9)
Igbo	6 (10.3)
Others	3 (5.1)
Total	58 (100)
Marital Status	
Single	24 (41.4)

Married	32 (55.2)
Widowed	2 (3.4)
Total	58 (100)
Educational Qualification	
No Formal Education	4 (6.9)
Primary	6 (10.3)
Secondary	25 (43.1)
Post-Secondary	23 (39.6)
Total	58 (100)
Employment Status	
Government	11 (19.0)
Private	7 (12.1)
Self	25 (43.1)
Unemployed	7 (12.0)
Students	8 (13.8)
Total	58 (100)

From Table 1, it showed that majority (39.7%) of the respondent were between age 30– 39years, few (25.9%) of them were of the age 20 – 29years, while minority (3.4%) of them were 60-69years. It was also deducted that, majority (60.3%) of the respondents were males while minority (39.7%) of them were females. Also, majority (43.1%) of the respondent had secondary school education, few (39.6%) of them had post-Secondary education, while minority (10.3% and 6.9%) of them had primary education and no formal education respectively. Moreover, majority (43.1%) of the respondents were self-employed, few (19.0%) of them were government employed, 13.8% of them were students, while minority (12.0%) were unemployed, with the mean value of 2.8772. It was also deducted that, majority (55.2%) of the respondents were married while minorities (3.4%) of them were widow.

Research Question 1: What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife

To determine the norms of the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care, the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores of the instrument were computed and the scores of the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care were categorized into three as low, moderate and high level respectively. The minimum and maximum scores were 50 and 99 with a mean and standard deviation of 75.02 and 10.76 respectively.

To compute the norms, the following method was used

$$\text{Mean} = 75.02$$

$$\text{SD} = 10.76$$

$$\text{Min} = 50$$

$$\text{Max} = 99$$

$$\bar{X} - \text{SD} = 75 - 10.76 = 64.24$$

$$\bar{X} + \text{SD} = 75 + 10.76 = 85.76$$

Range

Scores from 50 – 64: Low level

65 – 86: Moderate level

87 – 99: High level

Table 2: Patients' level of satisfaction with nursing care in OAUTHC?

Level	Frequenc y	Percent	\bar{X}	SD
Low	08	16.0	2	0.59
Moderate	33	66.0		
High	09	18.0		
Total	50	100.0		

The results from Table 2 showed that the largest percentage (66.0%) of the patients in OAUTHC had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing. Figure i further revealed the level of satisfaction with nursing care in OAUTHC at a glance

Figure i: Bar Chart showing level of satisfaction with nursing care in OAUTHC

Research Question 2: What is the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo

To determine the norms of the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care, the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum scores of the instrument were computed and the scores of the level of patients' satisfaction with nursing care were categorized into three as low, moderate and high level respectively. The minimum and maximum scores were 61 and 89 with a mean and standard deviation of 75.38 and 10.43 respectively.

To compute the norms, the following method was used

$$\text{Mean} = 75.38$$

$$\text{SD} = 10.43$$

$$\text{Min} = 61$$

$$\text{Max} = 89$$

$$\bar{X} - \text{SD} = 75.38 - 10.43 = 64.95$$

$$\bar{X} + \text{SD} = 75.38 + 10.43 = 85.81$$

Range

Scores from 61 – 65: Low level

66 - 86 Moderate level

87 – 89: High level

Table 3: Patients' level of satisfaction with nursing care in LAUTECH?

Level	Frequenc		\bar{X}	SD
	y	Percent		
Low	02	25.0	1.88	0.64
Moderate	05	62.5		
High	01	12.5		
Total	08	100.0		

The results from Table 3 showed that the largest percentage (62.5%) of the patients in LAUTECH had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing. Figure ii further revealed the level of satisfaction with nursing care in LAUTECH at a glance

Figure ii: Bar Chart showing level of satisfaction with nursing care in LAUTECH

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo

To test this hypothesis, responses of the patients in the two hospitals to items in Sections B of the questionnaire were computed. The difference between the patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo was examined using t-test statistical analysis.

Table 4: Difference between patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in OAUTHC and LAUTECH

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	Df	t-cal	P-value
OAUTHC	50	2.00	0.59	56	.498	0.699
LAUTECH	8	1.88	0.64			

P>0.05

Table 4 showed that the t-cal value of 0.498 was not significant at 0.05 level because the P-value (0.699) > 0.05. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that 66.0% of the patients in OAUTHC had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing while 62.5% of the patients in LAUTECH also had moderate level of satisfaction with nursing. The result showed the evidence of moderate quality service to the majority of surgical orthopaedic patients in the two settings understudy. Patients' satisfaction level is an indicator for evaluating quality of health service (Kingdon & Newman, 2013; Mishra & Gupta, 2012).

It was also revealed that there was no significant difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo. Patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in both hospitals was almost at the same level. Nursing care plays a major role in the health care services. Orthopaedic patients require a greater level of care as a result of several possible complications, increased vulnerability, potential cardio-pulmonary compromise and requirement of general concerns. Management of these complications requires understanding of preoperative conditions, intra-operative management and early recognition of any signs and treatment of postoperative complications. Delayed and inappropriate care can lead to poor outcomes and avoidable deaths (Al Qahtani & Al Dahi, 2015).

Conclusion

It is concluded from the findings of the study that there was no difference in patient's level of satisfaction with nursing care in Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching Hospitals Complex (OAUTHC), Ile-Ife and Ladoke Akintola University Teaching Hospital (LAUTECH), Osogbo.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings from this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Nursing care in the two hospitals (OAUTHC and LAUTECH) in Osun State should be adequately improved so as to achieve high level of the patient's satisfaction with nursing care
2. Majority of the accident victims that come into the hospital end up in Orthopaedic wards, this fact signifies the need for improved health care for patients in the orthopaedic wards.

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